

Common Property of Infinite Graph: Repeat of Finite Topology

무한 그래프의 일반 속성 : 유한한 위상의 반복

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Abstract

[한글] 무한한 연결 또는 정점을 가지는 그래프는 유한한 위상의 반복으로 정의 가능하다. 이러한 반복되는 유한한 위상 또한 그래프이다.

[English] Infinite graph which has infinite nodes or edges can be defined with repeat of finite graph.

1 Introduction

All the notations and preconditions follow the book referenced[Do Carmo(2016), Croom(2016), 김성기(2011), Fraleigh and Brand(2020), Rudin(1976)].

This paper will encounter simple fact that infinite graph is made up of finite graphs.

2 Countable Guaranteed: Compactness to Infinity

Theorem 1. *Graph $G(Node N, Edge E)$ is in relation that must be expressionable in $n \times n$ matrix.*

This theorem is so obvious. Then we can go on to next obvious.

Theorem 2. *Every graph is a repeat of compact graphs.*

This theorem is so obvious also. Then we can go to next obvious door.

Theorem 3. *Every graph is a repeat of in repeated connection of compact graphs that is in representation of $\forall n \times \forall n$ matrix.*

3 Matrix Multiplication

For next stage, it is obvious that multiplication of two matrices implies relation of two graph into one new graph.

Theorem 4. *With $n \times n$ matrix graph multiplied with $n \times n$ graph with nodes and edges conserved, new graph of repeatable count of minimum graph is derived.*

For example:

$$\begin{array}{c|cccc} & a & b & c & \cdots \\ \hline a & aa & ab & ac & \cdots \\ b & ba & bb & bc & \cdots \\ c & ca & cb & cc & \cdots \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots \end{array} \times \begin{array}{c|cccc} & d & e & f & \cdots \\ \hline d & dd & de & df & \cdots \\ e & ed & ee & ef & \cdots \\ f & fd & fe & ff & \cdots \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots \end{array} = \begin{array}{c|cccc} & g & h & i & \cdots \\ \hline g & gg & gh & gi & \cdots \\ h & hg & hh & hi & \cdots \\ i & ig & ih & ii & \cdots \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots \end{array}$$

In case of $gg = aa \cdot dd + ab \cdot ed + ac \cdot fd + \cdots$, any cardinal weight that gg can have implies the number of cases in combination of initial integer lattice, which represents repeatable compact 2 node 1 edge primitive graph.

Theorem 5. *Number of compact graphs repeated in larger graph is partial result from matrix multiplication, result $n \times n$ to $x \times y$ where $0 \leq x, y \leq n$.*

4 Fractals are Orthogonal

Then for the next stage, fractals can be derived as an orthogonal representation of matrix multiplication.

$$\begin{array}{c|cc} & a & b \\ \hline a & aa & ab \\ b & ba & bb \end{array} \times \left(\begin{array}{c|cc} & a & b \\ \hline a & aa & ab \\ b & ba & bb \end{array} \right)^T = \begin{array}{c|cc|cc} & & c & & d \\ \hline c & \boxed{aa \cdot aa + ab \cdot ab} & & \boxed{aa \cdot ba + ab \cdot bb} \\ d & \boxed{ba \cdot aa + bb \cdot ab} & & \boxed{ba \cdot ba + bb \cdot bb} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c|ccc} & a & b & c \\ \hline a & aa & ab & ac \\ b & ba & bb & bc \\ c & ca & cb & cc \end{array} \times \left(\begin{array}{c|ccc} & a & b & c \\ \hline a & aa & ab & ac \\ b & ba & bb & bc \\ c & ca & cb & cc \end{array} \right)^T$$

$$= \begin{array}{c|ccc|ccc|ccc} & & & c & & & d & & & e \\ \hline c & \boxed{aa \cdot aa + ab \cdot ab} & + ac \cdot ac & & \boxed{aa \cdot ba + ab \cdot bb} & + ac \cdot bc & & aa \cdot ca + ab \cdot cb + ac \cdot cc \\ d & \boxed{ba \cdot aa + bb \cdot ab} & + bc \cdot ac & & \boxed{ba \cdot ba + bb \cdot bb} & + bc \cdot bc & & ba \cdot ca + bb \cdot cb + bc \cdot cc \\ e & ca \cdot aa + cb \cdot ab + cc \cdot ac & & & ca \cdot ba + cb \cdot bb + cc \cdot bc & & & ca \cdot ca + cb \cdot cb + cc \cdot cc \end{array}$$

5 Dichotomy of Eigenvalue and SVD in Graph

If any graph can be split into another graph in relation of $G = G_1 G_2$ by eigenvalue or SVD, the relation of repeatable count splits into two graphs. The covariance then matters as common fractal in graphs.

Theorem 6. *If G_1 being covariance matrix with matrix decomposition, G and G_2 have common fractal as G_1 .*

References

- [Do Carmo(2016)] Manfredo P Do Carmo. *Differential geometry of curves and surfaces: revised and updated second edition*. Courier Dover Publications, 2016.
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- [Rudin(1976)] Walter Rudin. *Principles of mathematical analysis (int'l ed)*. McGraw-Hill Professional, New York, NY, 3 edition, September 1976.